

TEACHER'S PERSPECTIVE ON IMPLEMENTING (NEP 2020): CHALLENGES AND ISSUES

Dr. Shalini Rana¹, M.M. Mattoo² and Purvi Chandan³

- 1) Assistant Professor in English. Govt. College of Education Jammu J&K
shalinirana32@gmail.com
- 2) Associate Professor in Education. Govt. Degree College Chatroo Kishtwar J&K,
mattoomussarat@gmail.com
- 3) B.Ed integrated. COE. Jammu. purvichandan2407@gmail.com

Pages No: 20-34

Abstract: *The National Education Policy (2020) aims to revolutionize and improve the Indian education system by promoting progressive social and economic growth through experiential learning. The policy envisages broad based, multi-disciplinary, holistic under graduate education with flexible curricula, creative combinations of subjects, integration of vocational education and multiple entry and exit points with appropriate certification. The policy introduces a whole gamut of changes and reads largely as a very progressive document, with a firm grasp on the current socio-economic scenario and the prospect of future uncertainty. The changes that NEP 2020 has recommended were something that many educationists were waiting to come true. Transforming whole Indian educational system was not easy and hence it faces several challenges and other issues for its implementation. This research paper focuses on "Teacher's Perspective on Implementing (NEP 2020) "Challenges And Issues." A quantitative study. Population for the present study was undergraduate college teachers and the sample of 114 teachers was chosen by using multistage random sampling. Study analyzed the requirement of NEP and proposes the changes to improve its implementation. This paper not only described the challenges faced by the college teachers but provides a roadmap for the successful implementation of this policy and how to make Indian educational system to be recognized globally.*

Key Words: *NEP 2020, Experiential Based Learning, Holistic, Curricula, Vocational, Socio-Economic, quantitative*

INTRODUCTION

The New Education Policy announced by the Government of India (NEP 2020) was a welcome shift and refreshing news in the midst of all the negativity surrounding the world as a result of the issues created by the Covid-19 pandemic. Many people were completely surprised when the NEP 2020 announcement was made. Many educationists were unprepared for the reforms proposed by NEP 2020. The new NEP was implemented with the goal of formalizing system modifications from the school to the college/university levels. Keeping the changing circumstances in mind, future educational content will concentrate on key concepts, ideas, applications, and problem-solving approaches.

The National Education Policy is expected to have a good and long lasting impact on the country's higher education sector. The policy of establishing multi-disciplinary institutes will result in a revitalized focus on all fields, such as arts and humanities, and this type of education will assist students in learning and growing holistically. As a result, students will

have a stronger knowledge foundation to stand on. The implementation of a single standard entrance exam is another great step that will reduce the stress of several competitive tests and the pressure of studying for so many of them. It will also ensure that all future student have equal opportunities. Establishing an academic bank of credit (ABC) is an excellent idea for storing the academic credits that students acquire by taking courses at several recognized higher education institutions. The new higher education regulatory framework will ensure that unique administrative, accrediting, finance, and academic standard-setting functions are carried out by independent, autonomous, and recognized governing bodies. The NEP is intended to improve educational quality by providing access, equity, and future proofing. Four years after its inception, the policy trajectory, implementation issues, and local wins provide a wealth of learning that illuminate its revolutionary potential. Significant progress have been made, but obstacles remain, such as digital divide issues and the need for better teacher preparation. Progressive local efforts demonstrate the NEP's revolutionary potential. Jammu and Kashmir emphasizes the importance of implementing the NEP 2020 on time. This policy reflects the objectives of parents, teachers, students, and education specialists, and it seeks to solve the difficulties facing the next generation. In recent years, the local UT government has addressed concerns and apprehensions about the terms of this policy, ensuring that every vital part of this educational policy is implemented on time. Although some progress has been made in north India specially in Jammu and Kashmir, but still some issue are still to be addressed in connection with its proper implementation.

REVIEW

The National Education Policy (NEP 2020) creates a good platform for raising the country's educational standards to international levels. Indian society has undergone significant shift in recent decades. The NEP 2020 reflects changing HEI expectations and technological advancements that have resulted in hybrid ways of learning, and it is aimed to provide world-class education and improve the skill sets of learners and teachers (2018 Min Hong). Kalyani (2020) conducted a study wherein he emphasizes how this multidisciplinary framework is changing the Indian educational system by providing a thorough curriculum that incorporates conventional academic topics with abilities and principles. The goal of the strategy is to improve both cognitive and non-cognitive learning outcomes by including courses like physical education, arts, and vocational training, giving children the foundational knowledge and abilities they will need for success in the future. In this study he emphasized that in order to serve the many demands of its populace and modernize India's educational system to meet international standards, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a revolutionary step.

Nitul Sharma & Neelam Kaithal (2024) in their paper on issues and challenges of NEP (National Education Policy) 2020 in primary education focuses on key issues and challenges related to the implementation of NEP 2020 in primary education. They came to conclusion that successful implementation of this policy faces numerous challenges, including infrastructural deficits, teacher shortages, multilingual education complexities and resource constraints. Addressing these challenges will require significant investment, policy support, and community engagement. By overcoming these barriers, NEP 2020 can lay the foundation for an equitable and high-quality education system that benefits all children in India.

A thorough review of the literature shows that NEP 2020 is still in trial stage and not much research has been done so far with regard to challenges and issues teacher in particular and masses in general are facing. The present study aims to fulfill the significant gap by analyzing the New Indian National Education Policy 2020 with respect to challenges that college teachers are facing for its implementation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary purpose of this research paper was to determine the teacher's attitude towards implementation of (NEP 2020). "Challenges and Issues." A random sampling technique was used in the selection of the teachers. For this purpose self made tool "Challenges in successful implementation of NEP 2020 (CSN-NEP2020)" was used. Data were collected via google forms by sending the tool to their email address. Furthermore, the data were analyzed by using excel and SPSS software.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

This study was carried out to know the challenges and issues colleges teachers are facing for implementing this policy. Apart from this study will help students, teachers and other individuals grasp the changes, opportunities and challenges it introduces, enabling them to contribute to the policy's successful implementation and ultimately improve India's educational landscape.

POPULATION

In the present study all the college teachers of union territory of Jammu and Kashmir formed the population of the study.

SAMPLE

The sample for the current study comprised of 104 college teachers who were randomly selected from Union Territory of Jammu & Kashmir.

DATAANALYSIS

The data was analysed with the help of item wise percentage and pie-charts manually and through excel.

RESULT

Item wise result of the study is summarized as below.

Out of 114 respondents 61.4% of respondents are very familiar with NEP 2020, indicating a strong level of awareness about the policy, 34.2% are somewhat familiar, showing that a substantial portion has a general understanding, though they may not be deeply knowledgeable and 4.4% are not very familiar, suggesting a small portion of respondents have limited familiarity with NEP 2020 and None of the respondents are "not familiar at all," which implies that everyone has at least some level of awareness about NEP 2020.

To what extent has NEP 2020 improved the quality of teacher education?
114 responses

The data analysis of 114 responses exhibits that most people (54.4%) feel NEP 2020 has significantly improved teacher education. A good portion (39.5%) thinks it has somewhat improved, meaning they see some positive effects but may be not as big of a change. A small percentage (3.5%) is not sure if NEP 2020 has made a difference, which could indicate a lack of information or awareness, very few (2.6%) believe there has been no improvement. This suggests that NEP 2020 has had some positive effect on most people's perceptions.

Has the introduction of multidisciplinary approaches in teacher education (as per NEP 2020) improved teacher training?
114 responses

Out of 114 respondents 57.9% of respondents believe that the introduction of multidisciplinary approaches has significantly improved teacher training. This is the highest percentage, suggesting a strong positive view and 37.7% think it has somewhat improved teacher training, indicating that while they see improvements, it may not be as dramatic, Only 2.6% are not sure about the impact, which shows that most people have an opinion on the matter, whereas 1.8% believe that there has been no improvement with the introduction of multidisciplinary approaches.

To what extent has NEP 2020's emphasis on technology integration improved teacher education?
114 responses

55.8% of respondents feel that the technology integration under NEP 2020 has had a very positive impact on teacher education. This indicates that most people see a significant benefit to the inclusion of technology in teacher training programs. 41.6% believe the impact has been somewhat positive, suggesting that the integration of technology has been beneficial but to a lesser extent whereas 2.7% say there has been

no impact at all, which is a small portion of the respondents.

Has NEP 2020 adequately addressed the need for continuous professional development of teacher educators?
114 responses

Out of 114 responses 61.4% of the respondents believe that NEP 2020 has fully addressed the need for continuous professional development of teacher educators, indicating strong approval of the policy in this area, 28.9% feel that NEP 2020 has partially addressed this need, suggesting that while some improvements have been made, there may be room for further action. 6.1% believe that NEP 2020 has not addressed this need at all, indicating some dissatisfaction or apperception of inadequate focus on professional development and 3.5% are unsure, which could reflect uncertainty or lack of direct experience with the policy's implementation in this specific area.

Has NEP 2020 improved the balance between theoretical knowledge and practical teaching experience?
114 responses

56.1% of respondents believe that NEP 2020 has significantly improved the balance between theoretical knowledge and practical teaching experience, showing strong approval in this area, 39.5% feel that NEP 2020 has somewhat improved the balance, indicating that while there is some improvement, it may not be considered transformative. Only 2.6% report that there has been no improvement, suggesting that a very small proportion believes the balance has remained unchanged whereas 1.8% are unsure, possibly due to lack of direct experience with or information about the policy's impact on this balance.

To what extent do you think NEP 2020 has promoted social inclusion and diversity in teacher education?
114 responses

Out of 114 respondents 50% of respondents believe that NEP 2020 has promoted social inclusion and diversity to a great extent, indicating strong approval of the policy's efforts in this area, 41.2% feel that it has promoted inclusion and diversity to some extent, suggesting that while there have been some efforts, the impact might not

be as significant for everyone and 8.8% believe that NEP 2020 has not done much to promote social inclusion and diversity, indicating some dissatisfaction or perception of limited progress in this area.

How effective has NEP 2020 been in shaping teacher education?
114 responses

Result shows that 54.4% of the respondents believe that NEP 2020 has been very effective in shaping teachers which is the majority opinion, 33.3% of respondents feel it has been somewhat effective, meaning they see some positive change, but perhaps not as substantial as those who consider it very effective. 11.4% of respondents are neutral, meaning they might not have a strong opinion or feel the impact is unclear. Only 0.9% think NEP 2020 has been not effective in shaping teacher education, which represents a very small group.

To what extent has NEP 2020 led to changes in training programs for teacher educators?
114 responses

On the bases of analysis study shows 53.5% of respondents believe that NEP 2020 has led to significant changes in training programs for teacher educators, indicating a strong perception of impact in this area and 42.1% think that NEP 2020 has led to some changes, which means there has been some impact, but it might not be seen as transformational by everyone, 3.5% are not sure, possibly due to a lack of direct experience or information on the changes. Only 0.9% believes there have been no changes, suggesting that the majority perceives some level of impact from NEP 2020.

How much has NEP 2020 encouraged collaborative learning among teacher educators?
114 responses

This result of the analysis signifies that 80.7% of respondents (54.4% + 26.3%) feel that NEP 2020 has encouraged collaborative learning either to a high or very high extent, indicating a strong positive perception of the policy's impact on promoting collaboration among teacher educators whereas 18.4% feel that it has promoted collaborative learning to a moderate extent, meaning some improvements have been made, but the effects might not be as profound or universal. A very small proportion, 0.9%, feel that NEP 2020 has not encouraged collaborative learning at all, suggesting

that the policy has largely succeeded in fostering collaboration.

Has NEP 2020 encouraged a more student-centered approach in teacher education?
114 responses

Approximately 98.3% of respondents (65.8% + 32.5%) believe that NEP 2020 has encouraged a more student-centered approach in teacher education, with the majority (65.8%) seeing significant change, 32.5% feel that the change has been moderate, meaning that the shift towards a student-centered approach has been noticed but may not have been fully realized or implemented across all teacher education programs and 0.9% feel there has been no change, and another 0.9% are unsure, which is a small percentage overall

Has NEP 2020's focus on competency-based learning improved assessment methods for teachers?
114 responses

A good number i.e 95.6% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has improved assessment methods for teachers, with the majority (56.1%) seeing significant changes, 39.5% feel there has been some improvement, which indicates a strong positive shift but suggests there may still be room for further enhancement in the adoption of competency-based assessments whereas 3.5% being unsure and 0.9% seeing no change indicate that a very small portion of respondents have either not observed any changes or need more information to assess the impact.

How well do teacher educators understand the implementation of NEP 2020?
114 responses

Through analysis of 114 responses, 85.1% of respondents feel that teachers have a solid understanding of NEP 2020's implementation, with a strong majority (85.1%) stating that they understand it well or very well. A small group, 11.4%, believes that the understanding is somewhat well, which might suggest areas where more

in- depth training or clarification could be helpful. Only 3.5% of respondents feel that teacher educators understand the policy poorly, indicating that the majority are at least somewhat informed.

Has NEP 2020 provided greater flexibility in designing teacher education curricula?
114 responses

Out of 114 responses, 91.3% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has provided some form of flexibility in designing teacher education curricula, whether significant or moderate. The largest group, 47.4%, believes that the policy has made significant changes to curriculum flexibility, suggesting a noticeable impact, 43.9% feel there has been some flexibility, indicating a generally positive perception but suggesting that the extent of flexibility might not be fully realized or universally applied across all programs. A small minority 5.3% feel that the policy has not added flexibility, and 3.5% are not sure, indicating that for a few, the impact of NEP 2020 may be less clear or may not be as evident in their specific contexts.

Has NEP 2020 led to improvements in infrastructure and resources in teacher education institutions?
114 responses

On the bases of analysis, 91.3% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has had a positive impact on infrastructure and resources, with 47.4% noting significant improvements and 43.9% observing some improvements. The remaining 6.1% report no improvements, and 2.6% are unsure about the changes. These small percentages suggest that the overall impact of NEP 2020 on infrastructure and resources is largely positive.

Do you think NEP 2020 has strengthened accreditation and quality assurance in teacher education?
114 responses

Out of 114 responses, 92.1% of respondents believe that NEP 2020 has had a positive impact on accreditation and quality assurance in teacher education, with 53.5%

perceiving the changes as significant. Only 3.5% of respondents feel that there has been no improvement, suggesting that most respondents view the policy as beneficial in this regard and 4.4% of respondents are unsure, indicating that a small portion of respondents may need more information or clarity regarding the changes to accreditation and quality assurance under NEP 2020.

Has NEP 2020 provided sufficient financial support for teacher education institutions?
 114 responses

Out of 114 responses 76.3% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has provided some level of financial support, with 48.2% viewing it as somewhat sufficient and 28.1% perceiving the support as adequate. A 14.9% minority feels that the financial support is insufficient, indicating a need for more attention to funding in teacher education institutions and 8.8% of respondents are not sure about the financial support, which suggests that some institutions may not have clear information on the support provided under NEP 2020

Do you think NEP 2020 has effectively promoted arts, culture, and sports in teacher education?
 114 responses

95.7% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has positively impacted the promotion of arts, culture, and sports in colleges, with 55.3% of them believing it has been fully promoted. The 40.4% who feel it has been partially promoted suggest that while the policy has made progress, there may be areas where additional emphasis could be placed and 3.5% of respondents feel that there has been no improvement, which indicates that a small minority believes the policy has not sufficiently addressed this area whereas 0.9% are unsure, indicating that only a very small portion of respondents lack clarity on this aspect of the policy.

Has NEP 2020 addressed the needs of marginalized groups (tribal, economically weaker, disabled) in teacher education?
 114 responses

According to the data 81.6% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has positively addressed

the needs of marginalized groups in colleges, with 42.98% perceiving it as significantly addressed and 38.6% seeing it as somewhat addressed. Only 8.8% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has made no improvement, which suggests that there are still gaps that need to be addressed and 9.6% of respondents are unsure, indicating that some respondents may need more information or clarity regarding the impact of NEP 2020 on marginalized groups.

Has NEP 2020's focus on equity benefited teacher candidates from economically weaker backgrounds?
 114 responses

Result shows that 83.41% of respondents feel that NEP 2020's focus on equity has positively impacted teacher candidates from economically weaker backgrounds, with 36.04% perceiving the impact as significant and 47.37% seeing it as somewhat significant, 8.77% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has had no impact, suggesting that a small portion feels that the policy has not been effective for this group and 7.89% of respondents are not sure, indicating that some respondents may need more information or clarification on the specific benefits that economically weaker teacher candidates have gained from NEP 2020

Has NEP 2020 helped in reducing gender biases in teacher education programs?
 114 responses

91.23% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has positively reduced gender biases at undergraduate level, with 50.0% perceiving the reduction as significant and 41.23% seeing it as somewhat significant, 4.39% of respondents feel that NEP 2020 has made no change, suggesting that a small minority believes the policy has not made significant strides in reducing gender biases and 4.39% of respondents are unsure, indicating that a small proportion of respondents may need further clarification on the impact of NEP 2020 on gender biases in teacher education.

Have teachers received sufficient professional development to implement the curriculum changes of NEP 2020?
 114 responses

87.72% of respondents feel that teachers have received some form of sufficient professional development (either somewhat or significantly) to implement the curriculum changes of NEP 2020, 37.72% of respondents believe that the professional

development provided is significant, indicating that a good portion feels well-prepared to implement the curriculum changes and 50.0% feel the development is somewhat sufficient, implying that there might be gaps or areas where more in-depth training could be beneficial whereas 12.28% of respondents (9.65% + 2.63%) feel that the professional development has been inadequate, with a small portion feeling that teachers have received insufficient or no development at all.

Do teachers feel adequately supported by the administration in implementing NEP 2020 reforms?
 114 responses

Study also exhibits 87.72% of respondents feel that the administration has provided some level of support, either significantly or somewhat, in implementing NEP 2020 reforms, 43.86% of respondents feel the support has been significant, indicating that a solid proportion of teachers believe they have received strong backing and 43.86% feel the support has been somewhat significant, which suggests that while teachers feel supported, there may be room for more comprehensive or consistent support from the administration and 12.28% of respondents (8.77% + 3.51%) feel that the administration's support has been insufficient, with a smaller portion feeling completely unsupported.

Do teachers actively integrate the principles of experiential learning as outlined in NEP 2020?
 114 responses

On the bases of analysis 86.92% of respondents feel that they actively integrate experiential learning in their teaching to some extent, with 50.88% stating they integrate it significantly, 12.28% of respondents feel that they integrate little or none of the experiential learning principles, indicating areas where teachers may need additional resources to fully embrace the approach and 50.88% of teachers are strongly incorporating the experiential learning principles, which is a positive sign of NEP 2020's impact. Whereas 0.88% of respondents report no integration, which is minimal, but could be addressed by identifying barriers to implementation.

Have teachers contributed to fostering a multi-disciplinary approach in education as recommended by NEP 2020?
 114 responses

Analysis of data shows that 58.8% significantly and 33.3% of teachers to some extent feels that they are contributing in fostering a multi disciplinary approach in education by NEP 2020. Approximately 7 % teachers are of the view that they contribute lesser in comparison to 92 percent teacher who favours and contribute in connection with applying and fostering multidisciplinary approach in colleges.

Do teachers encourage students to engage in projects and research-based learning, as suggested by NEP 2020?
114 responses

58.8% of teachers significantly encourage students to engage in projects and research-based learning, which is a strong positive response and shows good alignment with the NEP 2020 goals, 38.6% of teachers somewhat encourage such learning methods, meaning while there is some effort, it may not be fully integrated or consistent across all classrooms. Only 1.4% of teachers report not encouraging project-based or research-based learning, suggesting that the vast majority are at least somewhat engaged in this approach

Are teachers able to address the diverse learning needs of students, as emphasized in NEP 2020?
114 responses

Out of 114 responses, 54.4% of teachers report that they can significantly address the diverse learning needs of students, which indicates that a majority are successfully adapting their teaching methods to accommodate various student needs, in line with the NEP 2020 guidelines, 37.7% of teachers say they can somewhat address these needs, suggesting that while there is some progress, it might not be as comprehensive or consistent as required by NEP 2020 and 7.9% of teachers feel they are unable to address these diverse needs much, or at all. This highlight to areas where there might be gaps in teacher training, resources, or support to effectively manage diverse learning needs.

Do teachers collaborate with parents and communities to implement NEP 2020's vision of holistic development?
114 responses

Out of 114 responses, 58.1% of teachers report that they significantly collaborate with parents and communities, which indicates a strong effort to involve these stakeholders in supporting the holistic development of students, as per NEP 2020's emphasis on community involvement whereas 36% of teachers say they collaborate somewhat, meaning while there is some engagement, it may not be consistent or widespread across all areas of holistic development and 5.9% of teachers report that they do not collaborate much or at all, suggesting that there are areas where greater efforts are needed to strengthen the partnership between schools, parents, and communities.

Has NEP 2020 encouraged a more student-centered approach in teacher education?
114 responses

Result shows that 65.8% of teachers report that NEP 2020 has significantly encouraged a more student-centered approach in teacher education, which shows strong alignment with the policy's emphasis on moving away from traditional teacher-centered methods to a more learner- focused frame work and 32.5% of teachers say there has been some encouragement of this shift, suggesting that while there is progress, it may not be fully integrated or consistently applied across all teacher education programs in which 1.7% of teachers either report no change or are not sure about the impact of NEP 2020 on teacher education, which might indicate a lack of awareness, resources, or full implementation in some regions or contexts

Has NEP 2020 contributed to making education more inclusive and equitable?
114 responses

Result of the study exhibits that 62.3% of teachers report that NEP 2020 has significantly contributed to making education more inclusive and equitable, indicating strong support for the policy's vision of greater inclusivity, access, and fairness in education and 35.1% of teachers say there has been some contribution, suggesting that while there is some progress, it might not be equally felt across all areas or schools whereas 2.6% of teachers are not sure or feel there has been no improvement, which could point to gaps in implementation, regional disparities, or a lack of awareness about the policy's efforts in this area.

CONCLUSIONS

National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in J and K has encountered several challenges and issues, particularly concerning teacher's attitudes. The NEP 2020 aims to bring transformative changes to the education system in India, focusing on holistic, learner-

centric education, the integration of technology, and a shift towards more critical thinking and creativity in classrooms. On the bases of analysis it is concluded that sufficient number of teachers in under graduate colleges are well aware and are acquainted with NEP 2020. Although in some domains there is mix type of response, however a good percentage of educators not only favours this policy but are satisfied with the changes made with regard to content, interaction and experiential based approach introduced by this policy. Whether it is related to awareness about the policy, introduction of multidisciplinary approaches, technology integration, balance between theoretical knowledge & practical teaching, improved assessment methods, positive impact on infrastructure & resources, incorporating the experiential learning principles, Administrative support, projects & research-based learning or inclusive & equitable learning all the teachers under this quantitative survey show very satisfactory response. Although it is too early to predict the success of this NEP 2020. But if we consider these findings, we hope challenges we are facing in its implementation will be dealt tactfully, because the vision of this policy is appealing and will definitely attract all those who are associated with teaching learning process and are aimed at to change the educational landscape of this country. In sum, while the NEP 2020 holds the potential for significant improvements in the Indian education system, teacher's attitudes and preparedness are critical to its success. Addressing the challenges they face, providing adequate support and fostering a positive attitude towards the policy will be key to ensuring that NEP 2020 delivers on its promise of transformative education.

SUGGESTIONS IN THE LIGHT OF THE CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

The attitude of teacher's towards the implementation of NEP 2020 plays a critical role in its success. Teachers are at the heart of the education system, and their perspective toward new policies directly impacts the effectiveness of these changes. The successful implementation of NEP 2020 largely depends on teacher's attitudes toward the policy. A positive, proactive, and open-minded approach is crucial to overcoming challenges like resistance to change, lack of training, and inadequate resources. It is essential to provide teachers with proper professional development, support, and a conducive environment for them to adjust to the new paradigm. Additionally, collaboration between teachers, parents, communities, and educational authorities will play a key role in overcoming the challenges and ensuring the smooth implementation of NEP 2020. Some significant points need to be taken care of for the proper implementation of this policy.

1. There is a need to conduct awareness programmes and training workshops for teachers in understanding NEP 2020.
2. For gross root implementations faculty development programmes need to be organized at District level.
3. Faculty at large must understand the mission under NEP 2020. We need to understand the shift from rote learning to more competency- based approaches.
4. Professional Development and Support.
5. Assessment and Evaluation Shifts.
6. National Mission for Mentoring (NMM) need to be established to connect experienced trainers and educators with new educators for the continuous support and guidance in connection with NEP 2020.

REFERENCES

Jaiswal. S. (2021). The Impact of National Education Policy 2020 on Higher education

- system. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(11), 69-75.
- Kalyani. P. (2020) An Empirical Study on NEP 2020 [National Education Policy] with Special Reference to the Future of Indian Education System and Its effects on the Stakeholders. *Journal of Management Engineering and Information Technology (JMEIT)* Volume 7 Issue 5, Oct 2020, Online ISSN: 2394 – 8124. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4159546
- Mahto, K. R. (2021). National Education Policy (NEP) 2020: A Path-Breaking Reform in Higher education system. *Journal of Education and Social Policy*, 6(3), 1-7.
- Malik. N, & Das. J. (2022). Vocational Education and Entrepreneurship in NEP 2020; *Rajasthani Journal*; vol: 1; Issue No.: 3; <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359685830> Vocational education and entrepreneurship in NEP 2020.
- Pathak.K.R.(2021).Reimagining Vocational Education and skill building; NCERT(nd);https://www.education.gov.in/shikshakparv/docs/background_note_Reimagining_Vocational_Education_Skill_building_revised.pdf
- Pathak. R, (2021). NEP 2020: A road map to Vocational Development; *Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*; vol-3; Issue-6; https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356001782_NEP_2020.A_road_map_to_Vocational_Development.
- Sharma. N., & Kaithal.N (2024). A study on issues and challenges of NEP (National Education Policy) 2020 in primary education. *National Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*. Volume 9, Issue 4, 2024, Page No. 1-3 <https://11nq.com/fKi93>
- Shukla, P. D., & Kaur, J. (2021). A Study on the Impact of National Education Policy 2020 on Higher education system. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(16), 94-100.
- Verma, R.(2021).New Education Policy2020: A Paradigm Shift in Higher education system. *Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, 7(1), 1-8.
- Vashist, A. (2021). National Education Policy 2020: An Insight into Reforms in Higher education system. *Journal of Education and Social Policy*, 6(2), 1-7.
- Yadav. J (2022) Vocational Skills and Nation Education Policy 2020; *International Journal of creative Research thoughts (IJCRT)*.vol-10; <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2205082.pdf>